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GASPOF

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Executive Summary

The EU-Horizon project **GASPOF** (Gas Sensing Platform based on Optical Fibers) is an ambitious initiative aimed at transforming remote gas detection technologies by leveraging existing fiber optic telecommunications infrastructure. Focused on enhancing sensitivity and miniaturization, the project integrates advanced optical gas spectroscopy to develop sensors for key gases such as carbon dioxide, methane and sulfur oxide. These sensors are designed for applications in urban greenhouse gas monitoring, volcanic activity surveillance, indoor air quality assessment, and pipeline safety.

Central to GASPOF's strategy is the engagement of a broad range of **stakeholders** —including industry experts, network operators, public administrators, and civil society representatives— ensuring that the system requirements and final sensor designs meet real-world needs. The ICTA-UAB team conducted a stakeholder mapping and requirements-gathering process through a carefully crafted questionnaire, distributed across the EU. The survey collected insights into current gas sensing needs, potential technical and regulatory barriers, and opportunities for integrating sensors with fiber optics.

The questionnaire, designed with input from all project partners, employed conditional logic to adapt to respondents' expertise (gas sensing or fiber optics) and was distributed through direct outreach and public events such as the WMO-IG3IS conference. A total of 53% of respondents had expertise in gas sensing, 29% in fiber optics, and notably, none had dual expertise —highlighting a key challenge for GASPOF in bridging these two domains.

Preliminary findings indicate promising market potential for gas sensors, particularly among SMEs and selected large companies. Over half of respondents reported access to fiber networks, an encouraging sign for deployment feasibility. The collected user requirements and priorities will now directly inform the technical development phase (Task 2.3), ensuring that sensor designs align with both operational needs and integration capabilities.

GASPOF thus sets a foundation for the next-generation, distributed gas sensing that is responsive to stakeholder input and capable of significantly enhancing environmental monitoring and safety across Europe.

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1. Introduction

The EU-Horizon project GASPOF is dedicated to advancing optical gas sensing technology by integrating innovative nodes into the fiber optic network of existing telecommunication infrastructure. This initiative capitalizes on recent breakthroughs in optical gas spectroscopy, aiming to overcome current limitations such as sensitivity and miniaturization, which have hindered the development of effective remote gas sensors. Our primary objectives are to design and develop sensors capable of detecting key gases including C carbon dioxide, methane and sulfur oxide, tailored for various applications like urban greenhouse gases monitoring, volcano activity monitoring, assessment of indoor air quality, and safety in gas pipelines.

Recognizing that successful sensor development requires collaboration with diverse stakeholders —end-users, experts, and industry partners— the project emphasizes incorporating their insights to ensure the final products are adaptable to different operational contexts and meeting use case requirements. By addressing these challenges effectively, GASPOF aims to significantly enhance the capabilities of remote gas sensing technology, thereby advancing environmental monitoring efforts and ensuring enhanced safety in a variety of scenarios.

The success of GASPOF will be achieved through the alignment of technical innovations with potential end-user requirements, while ensuring alignment with industry and societal expectations related to its pilot use cases. Therefore, the identification of the relevant stakeholders and the collection of their expertise constitutes a key step for the further development of the project.

The stakeholders were identified by the GASPOF consortium in a stakeholder mapping process, taking advantage of the expertise of the experts from industry and academia involved in the project. The questionnaire was designed to maximize the efficiency with highly targeted questions to collect the most useful information from the stakeholders, while adhering strictly to GDPR compliance. Therefore, only a minimum of background information was asked for (stakeholder group, location, plans to buy gas sensor soon, and access to fiber network).

The present report, Deliverable 2.1, describes the activities carried out in Task 2.1 “User & stakeholder groups categorization & collection of requirements” contained in Working Package 2 (WP2) “Preparation; User & application requirements, conceptual design”.

The results of the survey are analyzed and discussed in the present report and constitute useful information for the technical partners of GASPOF. The collected requirements and ranked priorities of potential end-users from various stakeholder groups will find entrance at several levels of the GASPOF project, being the most immediate use input for the technical requirements/targets for the GASPOF system components in T2.3 “System requirements and conceptual designs”.

2. Objectives

To achieve the aims stated above, the following objectives were formulated:

O1. *Stakeholder Identification*: Identification and categorization of key stakeholders, taking into account the four use-case scenarios (pervasive greenhouse gases monitoring, indoor air quality monitoring, volcanic activity monitoring, pipelines monitoring).

O2. *Requirements Collection*: Gathering and analyzing stakeholder requirements via a questionnaire-based study to identify the core needs of stakeholders engaged in gas monitoring, as well as key information regarding barriers and opportunities for the integration of gas sensors with fiber optics by network operators.

O3. *Analysis and Presentation of Results*: After the identification of stakeholder requirements, the information is processed and delivered to the GASPOF-consortium for further use.

2.1 Identification of stakeholder groups

Effective stakeholder engagement requires a thorough stakeholder mapping step in order to be able to identify the target audience and the communication strategy¹. In WP2, the entire GASPOF consortium worked first individually, then in case-study groups, and then as complete group at the physical meeting in Nicosia on the stakeholder mapping, guided by the objectives of the stakeholder engagement process. Soon it became evident that despite certain differences among the use-cases, there was a significant overlap between the identified stakeholders. This was especially true for the fiber network experts. Therefore, we decided to pool the stakeholders for the present tasks, with the case-study groups keeping in mind their particularities and their access to local and national networks for future outreach.

We identified the following stakeholders: network operators, photonic industry, telecommunication industry, other industry sectors, infrastructure operators for train and pipelines, engineering/construction companies, research institutions, administration or policy makers such as municipalities, and civil society. These stakeholders were selected and grouped to ensure a comprehensive representation of all relevant groups that could impact the project or be impacted by the project. This inclusive approach ensured that each sector's unique contributions were considered, from technical expertise and knowledge about infrastructure to innovation, regulation, community engagement, and ethical considerations, to obtain a comprehensive picture while targeting the information holders with the expert knowledge that was of main interest for the development of the gas sensors.

2.2 Design of the questionnaires

2.2.1 Strategy

This chapter outlines the design of the questionnaire-based survey that aimed to gather critical insights from stakeholders to ensure alignment with the project objectives.

The objectives of the questionnaire were threefold: first, to understand the stakeholder's needs regarding gas sensors, including current requirements and additional useful information; second, we aimed to understand potential barriers and concerns that could limit the integration of sensors into fiber networks and to identify necessary changes (including technical measures or legislation/policy) that could facilitate the widespread adoption of the GASPOF sensors, and third, the survey served also as an outreach opportunity aimed at informing stakeholders about the project.

¹Reed MS, Vella S, Challies E, et al (2018) A theory of participation: what makes stakeholder and public engagement in environmental management work? *Restoration Ecology* 26:S7–S17. <https://doi.org/10.1111/rec.12541>

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Given that GASPOF operates at an early Technology Readiness Level (TRL), our focus was on identifying the user requirements while designing our stakeholder communication strategy carefully to avoid unrealistic expectations from the public. By engaging stakeholders early, we wanted to establish benchmarks based on the gas sensor technologies they are currently using, while avoiding excessive discussion on "air quality" to maintain focus on technical feasibility.

To find a balance between the respondent's effort required to answer the questionnaire and the collection of results, we invested a significant amount of time into the design of the questionnaire.

The stakeholder engagement strategy and survey design were discussed in several group meetings and individual interviews with different members of the consortium, as well in a workshop with the entire consortium during a physical meeting in Nicosia. After the stakeholder mapping process and the consultation with the partners involved in the technical development of the sensors, it was decided to modify the initial approach described in the project proposal, where it was proposed to have different questionnaires for each use-case, and it was decided to use instead one unique questionnaire. The reasons were that the most relevant questions, especially the ones that will feed back into decisions during the technical development of the sensors, were common to all four case-studies.

The questionnaire was conducted using the platform *EUSurvey*². This accessible, EU-supported platform allows the creation of surveys without requiring personal data. It offers flexible survey tools with no restrictions on the number of questions or responses collected. The application provides basic automated results analysis and facilitates easy export of data, ensuring seamless data management. Meanwhile, EUSurvey is GDPR compliant and is a good example of technological infrastructure based in the European Union.

2.2.2 Questionnaire Structure

The design of the questionnaires considered that the completion of the questionnaire had to be not too much time consuming, with few but focused questions. The fact that GASPOF operates at the very interface between two usually not related technology fields (gas sensors and fiber networks) was identified as a challenge for the survey design in the sense that the questions need to be very specific to obtain useful answers, but simultaneously no respondent should have to answer questions that are outside of their field of expertise. There are virtually no experts that work in both fields simultaneously, but we wanted to avoid the split-up in different questionnaires. Luckily, the EUSurvey, the survey platform that was used offered the option of conditional questions that only appear depending on the answer to a previous question.

The questionnaire can be found in Appendix 1.

In the present questionnaire, we used question 1.6 for this purpose, asking whether the respondents had expertise in gas measurements or fiber networks, respectively (Figure 1). Depending on the answer, section 2 (gas measurements) and/or section 3 (fiber networks) appeared to be answered by the respondent.

1.6 Please indicate your expertise(s). **This will affect the selection of questions you will respond.**

- I am familiar with gas measurements
- I am familiar with fiber networks

Figure 1: Multiple choice question regarding the expertise of the respondents (gas measurements and/or fiber networks)

To obtain truly useful answers, we asked the stakeholders very specific and targeted questions. Due to the nature of the required information, open questions were required, while simultaneously being careful with the wording in order to avoid responses that are difficult to aggregate and interpret.

²<https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/>

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As mentioned above, the questionnaire was thus structured in three parts:

First, the respondents were asked for background information, such as stakeholder group (Q1.1) [Research/academia; Civil society representative; Public administration/policymaker; Photonics industry; Telecommunications industry; Other industry and Other], and location (Q1.2) [selectable among the 27 EU countries]. Other questions about company size (Q1.4), plans to purchase gas sensors in the near future (Q1.3) and access to a fiber network (Q1.5). This block ended with the question about the expertise (Q1.6, gas measurements or fiber networks) of the respondent, which determined whether Block 2, with questions related to gas sensing, or Block 3, with questions about fiber networks, followed.

2.2.3 Survey dissemination

The questionnaire was disseminated by the whole consortium in a targeted manner via direct email contacts to industry, researchers, administrations and other experts, and more broadly on social media (e.g., Figure 2). UAB, as leader of the tasks in WP2 provided a template for emails and social media posts. Additionally, the stakeholder engagement was presented as a poster at the WMO-IG3IS³ conference (Geneva), including a link to the survey (Appendix 2).

After opening the survey, we first had intended to close it on March 31st, but then decided to extend the duration until April 9th, to gain more responses, especially through the participation at the WMO conference, where we had the opportunity to reach a specialist audience of international experts involved in atmospheric monitoring.

Figure 2: Example a post for the dissemination of the survey on social media.

³<https://community.wmo.int/en/meetings/urban-greenhouse-gas-conference-and-stakeholder-summit-2025>

2.3 Survey Outcomes & Discussion

Upon closing the survey on the EUSurvey platform, the results were downloaded as a data sheet in the open .ods format. After bringing the data into shape for machine-readability with *LibreOffice* v24.2.7.2 (X86_64), data visualization was performed using *R* v3.4.3⁴ (R-Core Team 2013) and *R-Studio*⁵ (Rstudio 2013), using the packages “readODS”⁶ (Schutten et al. 2025) and “tidyverse”⁷ (Wickham et al. 2019) and “viridis”⁸ (Garnier 2018). Sample R-code of data visualization can be found in Appendix 3.

2.3.1 General information

Regarding the respondent’s institution (Figure 3 left, Question 1.1 “How would you characterize your institution?”), most of the respondents auto-identified as “industry” (total 41%), of these mainly “other industry”, but also “telecommunications industry” and “photonics industry” (Figure 3, left). As “research institution” identified 23 %, while “civil society representative”, and “public administration/policymaker” 12 % each.

The location of the participants (Figure 3, middle, Question 1.2 “Where are you located?”) was mainly Spain (47 %), Germany (24 %), France (18%), and Greece (12%), likely related with the respective dissemination effort by the GASPOF consortium members.

Figure 3: Stakeholder type (left), location (country) (middle), respectively, of the respondents and responses to the question Q1.3 (“We are considering to purchase gas sensing/measurement devices in the upcoming years.”), scale from 1 to 10 (right). The horizontal line represents the median.

Since GASPOF will develop a business plan for the exploitation of the results, we included a question to indicate the market potential of gas sensors (Figure 3 right, Q1.3 “We are considering to purchase gas sensing/measurement devices in the upcoming years.” Scale from 1 to 10). The median of the responses is slightly under 5, as not all respondents aim to purchase gas sensing equipment soon. However, several of the stakeholders expressed this intention, some even indicating a very high level of likelihood. This suggests that gas sensors might have indeed a marketing opportunity.

⁴R-Core Team (2013) R: A language and environment for statistical computing.

⁵RStudio (2013) RStudio: Integrated development environment for R. RStudio 2024.09.0+375 “Cranberry Hibiscus” Release (c8fc7aee6dc218d5687553f9041c6b1e5ea268ff, 2024-09-16) for Ubuntu Jammy

⁶Schutten G-J, Chan C, Brohan P, et al (2025) readODS: Read and Write ODS Files

⁷Wickham H, Averick M, Bryan J, et al (2019) Welcome to the tidyverse. *Journal of Open Source Software* 4:1686. <https://doi.org/10.21105/joss.01686>

⁸Garnier S (2018) viridis: default color maps from “matplotlib”

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The size of the companies among the respondents was well distributed, having Small and Medium Enterprises (SME) the highest proportion (Figure 4). The two respondents that identified as “large company”, which could be considered interesting in terms of purchasing power, answered to Q1.3 “We are considering to purchase gas sensing/measurement devices in the upcoming years”, with a 9 and a 2, respectively, on a scale from 1 to 10.

To understand the accessibility of fiber networks for stakeholders, Q1.5 “We have our own fiber network or easy access to a fiber network” was included. Network access is reported by over half of the respondents (53%).

Figure 4: Company size (left) and Access to fiber network of the stakeholders (right).

Question 1.6, about whether the stakeholder considered themselves as having expertise in gas measurements or fiber networks, had two purposes: First of all, the response to this question was used as input into the conditional selection of question. However, the responses give us also an idea whether we achieved to reach experts of the different fields. Of the respondents, 53 % reported having expertise in gas measurements, 29% in fiber networks, and 18% checked none of the boxes. The relative dominance of gas measurement experts can be explained in that gas measurements, despite being a specialist field, are an activity that is conducted in many institutions, while fiber optics are an infrastructure maintained by highly specialized industry.

It is noteworthy that no respondent described themselves as simultaneously having expertise in gas measurements and fiber networks, which underscores the novelty of the GASPOF approach, but identifies also a significant challenge in terms of communication and coordination to be able to merge the knowledge of these two fields.

2.3.1.1 Gas measurements

Q2.1 “Location of gas measurements”

Gas measurements are mostly taken Indoors and Outdoors (both locations were indicated by 50% of the respondents of Q2.1), while some end-users also measure in confined spaces or for individual protection (then with mobile devices). For technical reasons, the GASPOF sensors are not meaningful as mobile individual protection devices.

Q2.2 “Reasons for measurements”

Personnel/Public safety seems to be the most important motivation for gas measurements, indicated by 56% of the respondents. Monitoring, which encompasses, e.g., urban GHG measurements, is reportedly done by 44 % and production process emissions by 22% of the respondents, especially the large companies.

Q2.3 “Equipment used for gas measurements”

The respondents mentioned the following equipment as currently used to measure gases: PICARRO analyzer G-2301, Bosch Optical Gas Spectrometer V1.4; Envilyse Modell 405 nm; Radon scout, RTM2020 (SARAD); Envea, CO12e; IoT sensors and Honeywell CRIR M1.

This equipment represents a rather wide range of uses, technological abilities and price. This information is valuable to understand the benchmark against which GASPOF sensors will need to compete at potential customers. The technical specifications of the mentioned equipment (precision, sensitivity) will be used for the technical development of GASPOF sensors.

Q2.4 “Most important properties”

The collection of stakeholder requirements regarding gas sensor technological properties was one of the main objectives of Task 2.1. The question Q2.4 “Which properties do you consider most important for gas measurement devices?” provided valuable insights into the most desired properties (Figure 5). The stakeholders were asked to rank different properties of gas measurement devices regarding their importance. The ranking was then transformed into a score ranging from one to eight. Since we aimed to visualize not only the mean ranking, but also the distribution, the data was represented as violin plots, with the width of violins being proportional to the frequency of the rankings, and the height indicating the spread of the responses.

The findings revealed that “Low cost” emerged as the top priority for most respondents, indicating a strong emphasis on affordability in the design of gas sensors (Figure 5). This ranking underscores the growing importance of cost-effectiveness since budget constraints are significant and will not improve in the near term. Notwithstanding, some stakeholders ranked “low cost” not so highly, indicating the existence of potential customers with the need for high-performance sensors.

In addition to low cost, “Versatility (multiple gases, dynamic range)” was also highly valued by respondents, suggesting that flexibility was seen as essential for adaptability in various settings. Another key property ranked highly was “Low calibration and maintenance effort,” reflecting a preference for sensors that require less intervention, since maintenance requires specialized professionals and results in significant additional costs.

A noteworthy finding is that the ranking of precision, although overall rated as average, was the most variable of the properties. This indicates that the customer’s needs regarding precision of gas measurements depends on the application.

Properties such as “High sensitivity,” “Low downtime,” and “Robust measurements (under varying environmental conditions)” were ranked in the lower third by the respondents.

Interestingly, the property “Small size” was ranked as the least important among the respondents, indicating space limitations as not being a priority concern of the stakeholders. While this might seem counterintuitive at first glance, one respondent provided an exception: they specifically targeted sensors that are both small in size and low-cost, even if this would sacrifice precision or sensitivity. This highlights a niche market where space and affordability take precedence over absolute performance metrics.

Overall, these findings suggest that while cost, ease of use, and adaptability are critical priorities, there remains a gap in demand for sensors that balance affordability with sufficient precision or sensitivity. GASPOF will need to consider the trade-offs between performance and economic factors to meet emerging demands across industries.

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Figure 5: Ranking of properties of gas sensors from 1 to 8, where 1 is least and 8 is most important. From survey Question Q2.4 “Which properties do you consider most important for gas measurement devices?” The horizontal line represents the median

Q2.5 “Gases that are commonly measured together”

The combinations of gases that are commonly measured together as indicated by the respondents are presented in Table 1. This valuable information will enable the future development of sensors for such combinations and use-cases. The sensors currently developed in the frame of the GASPOF project will be able to measure CO₂ (including C isotopes in CO₂), CH₄, H₂O, CO and CHO_H (formaldehyde).

Table 1: Answers to the open question 2.5 “Are you aware of gases that are commonly measured together? Please state here”

Stakeholder	Gases commonly measured together
Research/academia	CO ₂ , CH ₄ , NO _x
Other Industry	CO and CO ₂ , Cl and NH ₃
Other Industry	CO ₂ and CO
Civil society representative	CO ₂ , methane and NO _x (agricultural emissions)
Other Industry	for Hydrogen : H ₂ , N ₂ , H ₂ O, CH ₄ , O ₂
Public administration/policymaker	NO _x , O ₃ , CO ₂ , CH ₄
Research/academia	Radon CO ₂ , Thoron

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Q2.6 and Q2.7 “Environmental conditions for gas measurements”

Since environmental conditions can interfere severely with the performance of gas sensors, two questions about this topic were included in the questionnaire to provide the technical teams with an idea what conditions the sensors might have to work in.

Question 2.6 (Figure 6) asked for harsh environmental conditions at the locations of the gas measurements, consisting in four options, multiple answers were allowed. Of the received n=6 responses, it is noteworthy that “Low air quality (particles, gases)” was included in all responses, while “Significant temperature changes” and “Temperature extremes (high or low)” received three and two mentions, respectively. Low air quality was also mentioned in solitary, while the other extreme conditions were mentioned always in combination with at least one other condition. Vibrations were not mentioned at all.

- 2.6 Are there harsh environmental conditions at the locations of the gas measurements?
- Temperature extremes (high or low)
 - Significant temperature changes
 - Vibrations
 - Low air quality (particles, other gases)

Figure 6: Question 2.6.

To obtain a more comprehensive picture of the variety of environments where they conduct gas measurements, the next question (Table 2, Q2.7) was included as an open question. Some of the answers describe environments with harsh conditions (e.g., “Industrial processes with furnaces”, this respondent also mentioned in Q2.6 three harsh conditions, namely “Low air quality (particles, gases)”, “Significant temperature changes” and “Temperature extremes (high or low)”, constituting the most heavy-duty use-case of the respondents). Such conditions will require special attention when developing the sensors and might require case-dependent technical adaptation. It is evident that GASPOF sensors will need to be versatile regarding their environmental conditions and be developed to have a broad optimum, although at a later stage, in the business analysis in WP6, the economic viability of product development for such use-cases will be assessed more in-depth.

Harsh environmental conditions

Significant temperature changes; Temperature extremes (high or low); Low air quality (particles, other gases)

-

Low air quality (particles, other gases)

Significant temperature changes; Low air quality (particles, other gases)

Temperature extremes (high or low); Low air quality (particles, other gases)

-

Further comments

Industrial processes with furnaces
monitoring of urban greenhouse gas

traffic intersections in Munich

We are interested in measuring gases in industrial processes, mainly hydrogen production, but also other uses.

we measure CO and CO₂ in industrial sites.
Sometimes the conditions are extreme, but mostly quite normal.

we would like to measure emissions in farms

Table 2: Answers to the open question 2.7 “Any further comments about the locations and/or environmental conditions for the gas measurements?”

Q2.8 “Technical conditions at the locations of measurement”

Since GASPOF aims to develop both “passive” as well as “active” sensors (the difference being in that the passive sensors do not require an external power source or cooling), we wanted to understand whether there is usually access to electricity, and the closeness to fiber network cables. Fiber network cables are frequently used in the large-scale infrastructure network, but then, once the connection point is passed into a facility, many buildings have copper wiring for internal data transmission. Therefore, question Q2.8 aimed to shed light on these two aspects.

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Of the n=10 respondents, all reported access to electricity at the location of measurement. Of the n=5 respondents that reported a close to a fiber network cable, all reported electricity, implying that an active sensor approach would be suitable for the sampled population. The passive sensor approach might still be important, especially for non-urban environments, such as the GASPOF use cases in areas of volcanic activity, or possibly the natural gas pipeline scenario.

2.3.1.2 Fiber Networks

Being the integration of the sensors into the fiber network an essential part of the project, this section of the questionnaire explored questions surrounding access to the fiber network and potential barriers.

Q3.1 Current fiber network monitoring

In the GASPOF project, in addition to spectroscopy-based approaches for gas sensing, the feasibility to use optical time domain reflectometry (OTDR) approaches, such as coherent correlation OTDR and fast Brillouin-OTDR (B-OTDR) are investigated due to their simplicity in integrating with existing telecommunications network infrastructure. Therefore, we asked the fiber network specialists Q3.1 (“How are you monitoring your fiber network for physical characteristics?”). Interestingly, all answers were either OTDR or specific, OTDR-based equipment (“T-BERD®/MTS-8000 DTSS”, and “LMG Aquasensor”⁹). The information that potential end-users are already using OTDR for monitoring physical characteristics such as temperature, temperature changes, vibration and humidity is very valuable and will be taken into account for the related GASPOF work packages.

Q3.2 Barriers to the integration of devices into fiber networks

Since fiber networks and data transmission constitute a critical infrastructure, the potential concerns of network operators might constitute a barrier to the integration of fiber-based gas sensors into fiber networks.

The answers to question Q3.2. (“How open are network operators to the idea to “plug in” sensing devices into their network when this constitutes minor decreases in signal quality?”) indicate that the stakeholders expect a considerable hesitancy from network operators (Figure 7, left). This needs to be taken into account in the communication strategy and steps to address this barrier with suitable measures that need to be taken.

In order to obtain more detailed information about possible barriers and potential solutions, Q3.5 (“What are barriers for access to the fiber networks? (e.g., security, damage on fiber network, ...)”) and Q 3.6 (“What actions could facilitate the adoption of fiber-based gas sensors? (e.g., policy changes)”) were included in the survey. Regarding the barriers, “security concerns” was mentioned by all respondents, followed by “data transmission” and “damage to the fiber network” (Table 3). These concerns need to be taken seriously. However, possible solutions, such as “a public body that certifies the companies involved in fiber monitoring” or “a certificate like ‘MEF 3.0 Carrier Ethernet’”, “open-source designs” as well as a “clear communication strategy” were mentioned as trust-building elements. These points will be taken into account in the further development of GASPOF.

⁹https://www.lancier-monitoring.de/fileadmin/content/downloads/Produkte/englisch/LMG_Aquasensor-Humidity_monitoring_in_fiber_optic_cables_english

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Figure 7: Expected openness of network operators to allow the integration of devices into their fiber network (Q3.2) (left), Free fibers in the network cables (Q3.3) (middle), on scales from 1 to 10. On the right, the answers to Q3.5 “What is the maximum size of a gas sensor to be installed in a chamber/manhole/handhole of your fiber network? (in cm)”. The horizontal line represents the median.

“What are barriers for access to the fiber networks? (e.g. security, damage on fiber network, ...)”

both security concerns as well as fear of someone damaging the network are a problem data transmission, security

our clients would be concerned for data security. security concern. And we would need proof that data transmission is not impaired the fiber network is a very sensitive infrastructure. Why not just using Wifi to transmit the gas measurement data?

“What actions could facilitate the adoption of fiber-based gas sensors? (e.g. policy changes)”

You would need a certificate, something like MEF 3.0 Carrier Ethernet

- Open source designs and a clear communication strategy in order make companies feel more secure that they are not installing spyware. a public body that certifies the companies involved in fiber monitoring to reduce concerns

Table 3: Answers to the open questions 3.5 and 3.6 regarding barriers and actions to facilitate adoption of fiber-based gas sensors.

Q3.3 Free channels for gas measurements

Since the primary purpose of fiber networks is the transmission of data, it is important not to impair this function. However, frequently, fiber cables have unused channels or even entire fibers¹⁰ that could be used for other purposes. This information is sensitive, since there is a conflict of interests by network operators, as they hesitate to be open about the proportion of so-called “dark fibers”. Despite this situation, we received several answers from industry experts to question Q3.3 (“Do you have free fibers or channels in your network that could be used for gas measurements?”) (Figure 7, middle), indicating that they have between zero and eight free channels in a cable. This information needs to be treated carefully, since this condition varies from network to network, but still indicates a certain potential for the GASPOF approach.

Asking more directly for the expert’s opinion on this potential in Q3.4 (“How many channels would you deem acceptable to be allocated for activities like gas measurements?”), the answers ranged between four and twelve channels (Figure 7, right).

¹⁰A fiber cable, depending on the type, can consist of several hundred individual fibers, The optical signal inside the fiber is coded in different frequencies, or channels. Current technologies like Wavelength Division Multiplexing (WDM) allow to increase the number of channels by reducing the wavelength of each channel.

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Q3.7 Maximum size of a gas sensor

Since miniaturization of gas sensors is also a goal of the GASPOF approach, we were interested in what the stakeholder considered the maximum size of a gas sensor. The answers to question Q3.7 (“What is the maximum size of a gas sensor to be installed in a chamber/manhole/handhole of your fiber network? (in cm)”) ranged from 25 to 88 cm, but most of the answers were 30 cm or less, indicating this as the preferred size for a gas sensor by surveyed experts.

Conclusions

Different stakeholder groups that are relevant to GASPOF were successfully identified and engaged. A questionnaire was designed to obtain relevant answers regarding stakeholder requirements and for prioritization of technical aspects in the development process of the sensors, as well as regarding potential barriers for the integration of gas sensors into fiber networks. In the present report, D2.1, the results of the stakeholder engagement process was analyzed and visualized. We conclude that the stakeholder engagement performed here in Task 2.1. achieved its objectives and provided useful information for other tasks and WPs in the project (Table 4).

First of all, we acknowledge that receiving a greater number of responses for our survey would have been desirable. However, despite the limited number of replies, we successfully gathered valuable insights by leveraging targeted dissemination efforts led by consortium members within key stakeholder groups. This proactive approach ensured that the survey reached those most aligned with its objectives, enhancing the relevance and utility of the data collected. Furthermore, our results-oriented questionnaire design was tailored to capture detailed feedback from experts, who provided rich qualitative insights into their perspectives.

While 17 responses may seem limited, they represent a substantial foundation for addressing the scope of our task. The data obtained is both diverse and meaningful, providing critical input from stakeholders with specialized expertise. Additionally, stakeholder engagement will continue through ongoing interactions with project partners, ensuring regular involvement without requiring additional survey responses.

The main challenge, however, was a structural one: despite the fact that significant improvements were made over the last years, some players still show a certain prevalence of a lack of understanding of the importance and the benefit of stakeholder engagement processes in research projects. It is noteworthy that the EU puts significant pressure on research projects to achieve widespread adoption of meaningful stakeholder engagement processes. Despite the fact that stakeholder engagement is usually required in EU-funded projects, it is often perceived or even executed in ways that do not optimize towards the ideal purpose of the stakeholder engagement process. This explains also the frequently observed survey-tiredness of experts, since these stakeholder engagement processes are sometimes seen as a form of *academic extractivism*, where researchers benefit from the work and input from others without providing an appropriate return.

These structural challenges are aggravated by the circumstance that GASPOF products are still at very early Technological Readiness Levels (TLR), which requires a highly specialized stakeholder engagement strategy. Technical specifications are not known at this early stage, and the engineers are already facing enough challenges to comply with the development of the sensors, thus making it difficult to integrate “wish lists” from potential customers that might be impossible to fulfill. Thus, the sophisticated design of the questionnaires was key to achieve the desired level of information. We had significant internal discussions around these challenges, and the ongoing process will be beneficial in the long-term.

Besides the direct results from the surveys, the stakeholder engagement strategy involved also consultations, interviews and literature research. During the work on WP2 and in direct interaction with stakeholders, we became aware that there are few legal regulations regarding gas concentrations for the general population, with notable exceptions being the gases considered as relevant for “air quality” (mainly Ozone, NO_x, particulate matter, SO₂ and CO) as well as the field of worker safety.

Although we aimed avoid the term “air quality” in the stakeholder engagement to avoid confusion and derailing, since the concept is dominated by gases that are outside the scope of GASPOF, there is nevertheless substantial input we can build on the previous work done in this very well-established field. Regarding air quality monitoring, there exist industry standards that should be taken into account. In July 2023, the CEN Technical Committee 264 ‘Air quality’ published two documents EN 15267-1:2023 ‘Air quality - Assessment of air quality monitoring equipment - Part 1: General principles of certification’ and EN 15267-2:2023 ‘Air quality - Assessment of air quality monitoring equipment - Part 2: Initial assessment of the manufacturer’s quality management system and post certification surveillance for the manufacturing process’ to improve measurement of air pollutants and support environmental

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protection. These documents cover explicitly quality standards for automated air quality monitoring equipment, and GASPOF can make use of the contained information.

The worker safety regulations are especially relevant for GASPOF sensors developed for the indoor gas measurement scenario, which could be used in industrial applications and other working places. Besides multiple regulations at the national and industry level, the most important regulation is likely the ATEX directive (EU DIRECTIVE 2014/34/EU), about explosives, which should be taken into consideration.

Finally, it needs to be noted that the respondents were not very enthusiastic about sharing their email addresses. This is a significant shift observed in the behavior of online survey participants and is likely related to a broader increase of awareness of a culture of privacy leading to hesitance to be open about personal data on the internet. This needs to be taken in account for future surveys: It might be that e.g. the properties of the explicitly privacy-friendly survey platform need to be communicated more, since the collection of contact lists constitutes an advantage for future dissemination efforts. Notwithstanding, especially for the fiber network operators that participated in the survey that disclosed highly sensitive information regarding free channels in their networks (Q3.3), the preservation of their anonymity might have been relevant.

Appendix 1: GASPOF questionnaire

The EU-Horizon project [GASPOF](#) aims to explore the potential of integrating innovative optical gas sensing nodes along optical fibers, towards their massive deployment in existing telecom infrastructures. New developments in optical gas spectroscopy have opened up new prospects for remote gas sensing applications, addressing the limitations of current analytical methods in terms of sensitivity, ease-of-use and miniaturization. Our project aims to develop sensors for a variety of gases, including CO₂ and methane, SO₂ and formaldehyde, for different use-cases such as Urban Greenhouse Gas monitoring, volcanoes, indoor air quality and gas pipelines.

Knowing the opinion of stakeholders is vital in order to integrate the needs of potential end-users and experts into the development of the sensors.

We would be very grateful if you could respond to the following questions (6 minutes aprox).

Please complete the survey latest by 8th April 2025.

For any issues or additional comments, please feel free to contact moritz.hallama@uab.cat

Looking forward receiving your response.

Best Regards

Mortiz Hallama, Gara Villalba and the GASPOF consortium

1 General information

1.1 How would you characterize your institution?

- Research/academia
- Civil society representative
- Public administration/policymaker
- Photonics industry
- Telecommunications industry
- Other industry
- Other

1.2 Where are you located?

- AT - Austria
- BE - Belgium
- BG - Bulgaria
- HR - Croatia

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- CY - Cyprus
- CZ - Czechia
- DK - Denmark
- EE - Estonia
- FI - Finland
- FR - France
- DE - Germany
- EL - Greece
- HU - Hungary
- IE - Ireland
- IT - Italy
- LV - Latvia
- LT - Lithuania
- LU - Luxembourg
- MT - Malta
- NL - Netherlands
- PL - Poland
- PT - Portugal
- RO - Romania
- SK - Slovak Republic
- SI - Slovenia
- ES - Spain
- SE - Sweden

1.3 We are considering to purchase gas sensing/measurement devices in the upcoming years.

1.4 How large is your company?

- Large
- SME
- Small

1.5 We have our own fiber network or easy access to a fiber network

- Yes
- No

1.6 Please indicate your expertise(s). **This will affect the selection of questions you will respond.**

- I am familiar with gas measurements
- I am familiar with fiber networks

2 Gas measurements

2.1 Please state how you measure gases (multiple choices possible)

- Indoor
- Confined

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- Outdoor
- Individual protection

2.2 What is the reason for measuring gases? (multiple options possible)

- Personnel/public safety
- Production process emissions
- Monitoring
- Other

2.3 Please state the equipment (if possible, company and model) you currently use to measure gas concentrations:

2.4 Which properties do you consider most important for gas measurement devices ?

Please rank these items, with the most important on top.

Use drag&drop or the up/down buttons to change the order or accept the initial order.

- High precision
- High sensitivity
- Low calibration and maintenance effort
- Low cost
- Low downtime
- Robust measurements (under varying environmental conditions)
- Small size
- Versatility (multiple gases, dynamic range)

2.5 Are you aware of gases that are commonly measured together? Please state here

2.6 Are there harsh environmental conditions at the locations of the gas measurements?

- Temperature extremes (high or low)
- Significant temperature changes
- Vibrations
- Low air quality (particles, other gases)

2.7 Any further comments about the locations and/or environmental conditions for the gas measurements?

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2.8 Technical conditions at the locations of measurement

- A fiber network cable is close
- There is access to electricity

3 Fiber network

3.1 How are you monitoring your fiber network for physical characteristics? (temperature, temperature changes, vibration...)

3.2 How open are network operators to the idea to "plug in" sensing devices into their network when this constitutes minor decreases in signal quality?

3.3 Do you have free fibers or channels in your network that could be used gas measurements?

3.4 How many channels would you deem acceptable to be allocated for activities like gas measurements?

3.5 What are barriers for access to the fiber networks? (e.g. security, damage on fiber network, ...)

3.6 What actions could facilitate the adoption of fiber-based gas sensors? (e.g. policy changes)

3.7 What is the maximum size of a gas sensor to be installed in a chamber/manhole/handhole of your fiber network? (in cm)

4 Further information

4.1 Please name any other stakeholders or potential end-users that should be contacted by our team

4.2 Anything else you want to tell us?

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4.3 Please add your email if you wish to receive the outcome of this survey, once completed, or further updates on the project.

By providing your email, you accept our [Data protection policy](#)

[We will use your email exclusively for the purpose of the dissemination of GASPOF results].

Appendix 2 GASPOF Survey Poster

Project description

The EU-Horizon project **GASPOF** aims to explore the potential of integrating innovative **optical gas sensing nodes along optical fibers** for remote gas sensing applications, addressing the limitations of current analytical methods in terms of sensitivity, ease-of-use and miniaturization.

Our project aims to develop sensors for a variety of gases, including CO₂ and methane for different use-cases such as urban greenhouse gas monitoring, volcanoes, indoor air quality and gas pipelines.

We need your expertise!

Knowing the opinion of stakeholders is vital to integrate the needs of potential end-users and experts into the development of the sensors. We would be very grateful if you could **respond to the survey below**, accessible via the QR code (3 minutes aprox) by 9th April 2025.

THANK YOU!

For any issues or additional comments, please contact moritz.hallama@uab.cat

Project Facts

Start date: 01/12/2024
 Duration: 48 months
 Funding: € 3,912,593.75
 Partners: 10
 Countries: 7

Call topic: HORIZON-CL4-2024-DIGITAL-EMERGING-01-54 - Smart Photonics for joint communication & sensing and access everywhere (Photonics Partnership)

Grant agreement ID: 101189654

Project website: <https://gasprof.eu/>

Link to the survey:

THANK YOU!!!

https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/GASPOF_Stakeholder_Survey

Key Objectives

- Develop the **optical-fiber-based Photo-thermal Spectroscopy (PTS)** sensing modality. The goal is to develop optical gas sensing nodes, pluggable to telecom fiber networks.
- Develop the **Laser Heterodyne Radiometry (LHR)** sensing setup. Develop a distributed sensing system for atmospheric composition analysis with high spatial resolution. The sunlight captured at different measurement points will be delivered to the LHR instrument using the fiber network.
- Exploit the fibers as physical parameters sensors and evaluate **CC-OTDR-based gas sensing**
- Validate the system in relevant case studies.
- Widely communicate results and facilitate large-scale results adoption

Use-cases

Urban Greenhouse Gases

Since atmospheric monitoring is frequently limited by high equipment costs, a distributed system of sensors could improve greatly the spatial resolution. An **optical-fiber-based LHR sensing system** will be validated in measuring greenhouse gases (CO₂, CH₄) as a function of altitude in the atmospheric column (**vertical profiling of gases**).

Location: Barcelona (Spain) and Thessaloniki (Greece)

Indoor Air Quality

Indoor air quality is largely impacted by CO₂ and volatile organic compounds (VOCs) levels. With a newly developed sensor, based on **photothermal spectroscopy**, GASPOF will exploit SenseCity, a Facility of Excellence within University Gustave Eiffel (Paris) to measure CO₂, CO, CH₄ and formaldehyde in an indoor setting.

Location: Paris (France)

Volcanic Activity

New PTS sensors will measure H₂O, SO₂, HCl, HF and CO₂. **Isotope composition of CO₂** can improve the accuracy of eruption forecasting. In parallel, a new sensing approach will be used to **measure vibrations** (seismic activity) & temperature using the OTDR approach, and we will also investigate the possibility of using CC-OTDR for gas sensing.

Location: Volcanic area of the Canary Islands (Spain)

Gas Leakage Detection

Preventing methane leakage from transmission pipelines constitutes an important tool to reduce methane emissions. In order to detect and resolve methane leaks, reliable and cost-effective sensors need to be developed.

Methane will be detected using the PTS sensing method, developing a **passive sensor** that relies on the NIR laser of the fiber network.

Location: Thessaloniki (Greece)

Appendix 3 – Sample R-code of data visualisation

```

# Deliverable 2.1 "User & stakeholders requirements report"
# www.gaspof.eu
# contact: moritz.hallama@uab.cat

# load libraries
library(readODS)

library(tidyverse)

#import GaspofSurvey_Locationset (make sure the path is correct!)
GaspofSurvey<- read_ods("~/Desktop/GasPof2024/RE_GASPOF - WP2
deliverables/Content_Export_GASPOF_Stakeholder_survey_GASPOFSurveyResults.ods",
sheet="Survey")

str(GaspofSurvey)

#####
#Figure 1.1 Stakeholder
GaspofSurvey_Stakeholder=GaspofSurvey%>%count(Stakeholder)#, sort=T)

# Compute percentages
GaspofSurvey_Stakeholder$fraction <- GaspofSurvey_Stakeholder$n /
sum(GaspofSurvey_Stakeholder$n)

# Compute the cumulative percentages (top of each rectangle)
GaspofSurvey_Stakeholder$ymax <- cumsum(GaspofSurvey_Stakeholder$fraction)

# Compute the bottom of each rectangle
GaspofSurvey_Stakeholder$ymin <- c(0, head(GaspofSurvey_Stakeholder$ymax, n=-1))

# Compute label position
GaspofSurvey_Stakeholder$labelPosition <- (GaspofSurvey_Stakeholder$ymax +
GaspofSurvey_Stakeholder$ymin) / 2

# Compute a good label
GaspofSurvey_Stakeholder$label <- paste0(GaspofSurvey_Stakeholder$Stakeholder, "\n ",
GaspofSurvey_Stakeholder$n)

# Make the plot
GaspofSurvey_StakeholderPlot=ggplot(GaspofSurvey_Stakeholder, aes(ymax=ymax, ymin=ymin,
xmax=4, xmin=3, fill=Stakeholder)) +
  geom_rect() +
  geom_label( x=3.5, aes(y=labelPosition, label=n), size=6) +
  scale_fill_brewer(palette=4) +
  coord_polar(theta="y") +
  xlim(c(2, 4)) +
  theme_void() #+ theme(legend.position = "none")

GaspofSurvey_StakeholderPlot

png("GaspofSurvey_Stakeholder_plot.png",width=500,height=500, res = 200, units="px")
GaspofSurvey_StakeholderPlot
dev.off()

#####
#Figure 1.2: Location
GaspofSurvey_Location=GaspofSurvey%>%count(Location)#, sort=T)

# Compute percentages
GaspofSurvey_Location$fraction <- GaspofSurvey_Location$n / sum(GaspofSurvey_Location$n)

# Compute the cumulative percentages (top of each rectangle)

```

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```

GaspofSurvey_Location$ymax <- cumsum(GaspofSurvey_Location$fraction)
# Compute the bottom of each rectangle
GaspofSurvey_Location$ymin <- c(0, head(GaspofSurvey_Location$ymax, n=-1))
# Compute label position
GaspofSurvey_Location$labelPosition <- (GaspofSurvey_Location$ymax +
GaspofSurvey_Location$ymin) / 2
# Compute a good label
GaspofSurvey_Location$label <- paste0(GaspofSurvey_Location$Location, "\n ",
GaspofSurvey_Location$n)
# Make the plot
GaspofSurvey_LocationPlot=ggplot(GaspofSurvey_Location, aes(ymax=ymax, ymin=ymin, xmax=4,
xmin=3, fill=Location)) +
  geom_rect() +
  geom_label( x=3.5, aes(y=labelPosition, label=label), size=6) +
  scale_fill_brewer(palette=4) +
  coord_polar(theta="y") +
  xlim(c(2, 4)) +
  theme_void() +
  theme(legend.position = "none")
GaspofSurvey_LocationPlot
png("GaspofSurvey_Location_plot.png",width=500,height=500, res = 200, units="px")
GaspofSurvey_LocationPlot
dev.off()

#####
#Figure 1.3: PurchaseSensor
# Make the plot
GaspofSurvey_PurchaseSensorPlot=ggplot(GaspofSurvey, aes(y=PurchaseSensor))+
  geom_violin(x)+
  # geom_label( x=3.5, aes(y=labelPosition, label=label), size=6)+
  scale_fill_brewer(palette=4) +
  #theme_void() +
  GaspofSurvey_PurchaseSensorPlot
# Violin chart
GaspofSurvey_PurchaseSensorPlot <- ggplot(GaspofSurvey, aes(y=PurchaseSensor,x="",
fill="Likelihood to purchase a sensor")) + # fill=name allow to automatically dedicate a
color for each group
  geom_violin(trim=T, draw_quantiles = 0.5)+
  scale_fill_brewer(palette=4) +
  ylab("Likelihood to purchase a gas sensor")+xlab("")+
  theme(legend.position = "none", axis.text.x = element_blank())
GaspofSurvey_PurchaseSensorPlot
png("GaspofSurvey_PurchaseSensor_plot.png",width=300,height=600, res = 200, units="px")
GaspofSurvey_PurchaseSensorPlot
dev.off()

```